

Conference and Proceedings

When the Brazilian DOCOMOMO Working Party stated its intention to host the Sixth International DOCOMOMO Conference, it was guided by the basic idea underlying the formation of our national working party in 1992: bringing together people and institutions scattered throughout Brazil that are interested in documenting, studying and debating the architecture and urbanism of the Modern Movement. At the same time, the aim was to bolster international debate about this subject with our counterparts in other countries. Since then, DOCOMOMO Brazil's meetings have been a rich and challenging collective experience.

In 1996, we announced our candidacy through a letter of intent from the Brazilian working party, presented during the Council Meeting of the Fourth International DOCOMOMO Conference in Slovakia. The title chosen for the conference, "The modern city facing the future," reflected the aim of discussing Modern Urbanism in light of the Brazilian experience of serving on the DOCOMOMO International Specialist Committee on Urbanism, then headed by Marco Aurélio Gomes. Another factor we considered when developing our bid to host the conference was the informal requests received from members of several other national working parties that the event be held in the city of Brasilia, which is recognized as one of the Modern Movement's most ambitious and successful accomplishments in the field of urbanism. The US working party also announced its candidacy to host the 2000 conference. The Council Meeting decided to postpone voting on the 2000 conference until February 1997, and asked the two candidates to submit more detailed proposals and commitments from support institutions.

Finally, we submitted a paper drafted in accordance with the "General Outlines for International DOCOMOMO Conferences" to DOCOMOMO International on February 4, 1997. It was presented to the members of the International Council, who voted in favor of holding the conference in Brasilia. The organizing institutions that signed the proposal included the Universidade Federal da Bahia (UFBA) – which since 1992 has housed the directorate of DOCOMOMO Brazil at its Graduate Department of Architecture and Urbanism – and the Universidade de Brasilia (UnB), which, through its School of Archi-

itecture, accepted the challenge of holding the conference in that celebrated city. Therefore, the conference's executive office was established at UnB under the direction of Professor Frederico de Holanda.

The Call for Papers presented the basic structure for the conference so as to better guide the submission of abstracts. Scientific Committee members helped write the introduction on the conference's theme, the central motivation of which was encouraging a critical analysis of the Modern Movement's urbanism experiences while seeking to identify the relevance (or lack thereof) of the continuity of their principles, with a view to achieving better quality in future urban-planning projects. More specific issues were also suggested for paper topics, such as the relationship between designed and real cities, urban and architectural form (the city as a designed unity), social commitment and political control, urban preservation and dynamics, universal proposals and individual realities, as well as topics such as authenticity, authorship, the aesthetic dimension and collective life.

The Scientific Committee met to make the final selection of papers in December 1999 in São Paulo City, with the support of the Biennial Foundation (Niemeyer, 1954), during the Third International Architecture Biennial and the Third Brazilian DOCOMOMO Seminar. We received 310 abstracts from 29 countries. Of these, we selected 51 abstracts for oral presentation and 40 for case-study panels to be exhibited at the conference. The Final Program was developed on the basis of the abstracts that were most closely related to the conference's central theme, and they were used to determine the thematic sessions. In addition to a session on the Main Theme, a special session on Brasilia was organized due to the large proportion of papers on that city. The International Executive Committee suggested making another change in the structure of previous conferences, which was including more guest speakers in the program.

The official opening of the conference and welcome cocktail party took place at Itamaraty Palace (Ministry of Foreign Affairs), one of the foremost buildings designed by Oscar Niemeyer, with gardens designed by Roberto Burle Marx. The Opening Session panel included the President of the In-

Lúcio Costa - "Relatório do Plano Piloto de Brasília", 1957.

ternational DOCOMOMO, Hubert-Jan Henket, representatives of the Universidade de Brasília and Universidade Federal da Bahia, the event's organizers, and architect Maria Elisa Costa, daughter of Lucio Costa, whom we wanted to honor. Then, renowned architect Kisho Kurokawa gave the keynote lecture. After the opening ceremony, everyone was invited to go on an architectural promenade to the building's garden terrace, where pianist Marcelo Bratke (grandson of Brazilian architect Oswaldo Bratke) awaited us to give a recital. We were thrilled to enjoy a carefully selected program of 20th-century works by composers ranging from Gershwin to Villa-Lobos. In the spirit of the DOCOMOMO conferences, this performance represented the role of nature in modern Brazilian music and its relationship with modern music around the world.

In the days that followed, the conference took place in two auditoriums in the main building of UnB – the Central Science Institute, another magnificent Niemeyer building. In addition to the Thematic Sessions, the Exhibition opened on the first night, and the DOCOMOMO International Council Meeting began on the second evening. Unfortunately, a closing general debate including guest speakers that was scheduled for the final afternoon of the conference had to be cancelled due to timing problems. The work ended in the early evening, shortly after a presentation by the Sixth DOCOMOMO International Conference team. After a three-day work marathon in which architecture students were markedly present, exhaustion gave way to a festive atmosphere during the closing party, held on a moonlit evening in the garden terrace of the National Congress building's annex in the Pilot Plan, which affords a splendid view of Three Powers Square.

In addition to the official program, guided tours to the most significant parts of the city were organized to give everyone a general idea of what the

accomplishment called Brasília is today. It was interesting to see first-time visitors' varying expectations and forms of appropriation of the city. In this regard, if the Sixth International DOCOMOMO Conference was an event on modern urbanism held in Brasília, it left us with the desire to organize a specific event on Brasília in the future.

We were also aware that many participants were visiting Brazil for the first time, and therefore we made a point of offering Additional Post-Conference Tours to five other important cities. A work team was formed in each city under the responsibility of Marta Camisassa (Belo Horizonte and Ouro Preto), Márcio Campos (Salvador), Mirthes Baffi (São Paulo) and the Niemeyer Foundation (Rio de Janeiro). Thanks to meticulous planning, participants had a chance to experience first hand the diversity and vastness of this country, which developed under the aegis of modernity.

On behalf of UFBA, the UnB and DOCOMOMO International, we would like to thank the institutions that supported us and believed in this conference. Our special thanks to Francisco Júnior and João Borges, from the UnB Graduate Department of Architecture and Urbanism (FAU/UnB), and Alejandra Muñoz, from UFBA, who worked alongside us with such dedication to ensure the conference's success.

Brasília "Rodoviária", 1990, DePHA/GDF Archives - S. Cavalcante.

Proceedings

The aim of this publication is to publish all the papers and lectures presented during the conference.

Strangely enough, one year after the event, long after its executive office was closed, we had received less than 30% of the papers, which prevented us from obtaining the funding required to publish them in good time. We then sought the help of the Brazilian DOCOMOMO working party to issue a third (and urgent) call for papers. Thanks to the cooperation of Hugo Segawa, Mirthes Baffi and Marina Donelli, we managed to collect nearly 80% of the papers. DOCOMOMO International was aware of the situation and suggested that we go ahead anyway.

This publication's structure follows the order of the conference's program. The complete papers have been revised and/or expanded by their authors, including added illustrations and captions. The solution devised for unsubmitted papers was to publish their abstracts (in italics), which we received prior to the conference.

Finally, we would like to extend our special thanks to Professor Flávia Garcia, the managing director of the UFBA Press, who took this publication in hand and produced and printed this book free of charge, despite the university's current financial difficulties.

This book is dedicated to Milton Santos, who died in 2001.

Anna Beatriz Galvão and Frederico de Holanda

Brasília "Praça dos Três Poderes", 1990, DePHA/GDF Archives - S. Cavalcante.